
Is Wealth a Weapon? Exploring the Link between GDP per Capita and Financial Crime

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Abstract

This study focused on ‘exploring the Link between GDP per Capita and Financial Crime’. One research question and one hypothesis guided the study. Works of literature pertinent to the study were reviewed. The population of 214 World Bank member countries as of the year 2021 also represents the sample. However, it was further stripped to 155 countries due to the absence of data for variables in some countries, which was refined by removing those countries from the sample. Data for the study were collected from the World Bank Governance (WGI) and Development Indicators (WDI). The level of financial crime data was mirrored using the control of corruption data. The year 2021, the most recent year available on the World Bank indicator database, was explored because the researcher sampled the total population, focusing on the global countries rather than comparing time series. The data were analysed, and all the results were computed using the R-studio. The results were tested using the regression analysis, including the t-test and the correlation coefficients, which were tested at a 0.05 level of significance to ensure solid evidence. This study found that the financial crime level of the sampled countries significantly increases at the slightest increase in the GDP per capita level. This study recommends that policymakers should adopt a multi-dimensional approach that goes beyond economic metrics, strengthening institutional frameworks, improving law enforcement, promoting ethical standards, and incorporating governance indicators into risk assessments.

Keywords: GDP per capita, Financial crime, Economic development, Wealth inequality

1.0 Introduction

Over the past few decades, there has been a greater understanding of the harm that financial crime activities including fraud, cybercrime, money laundering, embezzlement, insider trading, counterfeiting, tax evasion, bribery, and financing terrorism pose to global economies. The financial crime phenomenon is such a complex issue (Achim & Borlea, 2021), that its understanding, comprehension, and measurement remain complex and multi-faceted. (Hamid et al., 2013). Because not all instances of financial crime, such as fraud, embezzlement, and money laundering, are identified and documented, it is difficult to comprehend the scope of this problem. The menace as a global problem disrupts the stability and sanity of economies, both developed and developing, (Akanni et al. 2019). According to De Rosa et al. (2010), financial crime typically benefits the developed economy, whereas smaller economies are mostly the ones who commit it. Additionally, Akanni et al. (2019) noted that its severe negative impacts may lead to a decline in trust in countries' economy, which would hinder foreign direct investment in those countries.

The estimated costs of fraud and cybercrimes in 2018 were £4.7 billion and £1.1 billion, respectively, according to Heeks et al. (2018)'s official report to the UK's Home Office. NexisLexis Risk Solutions (2021)'s estimate of the global cost of financial crime compliance in 2021 was \$213.9 billion.

There would not be an over-emphasis on the depletion characteristics of financial crime, despite how deep and wide it is discussed or highlighted. Nations, institutions, and firms are not only ruined by financial crime activities like cybercrime, bribery, fraud, and insider trading, which has overwhelming consequences like financial instability, bankruptcy, and trauma-related suicide on individuals and the global world continually. (Akanni et al., 2019). The obvious complex and multi-faceted nature of the financial crime phenomena is of global concern, and understanding its determinants is essential for effective prevention and solution.

There have been suggestions on what influences or determines financial crime by various researchers like Akanni et al. (2019) and Buonanno (2003), who identified financial crime determinants as poverty, unemployment, insufficient remuneration, greed, high costs of living, peer or social pressure, laziness, ineffective investigation and prosecution of crimes, and absence of very serious consequences for committing crimes amongst others.

According to Achim et al. (2021), financial crime is determined by a variety of cultural, behavioural, political, social, and macroeconomic factors, including government efficacy, income, unemployment, inflation, interest rates, political stability, and GDP per capita. According to the UK Home Office (2016), six main factors contribute to crime: opportunity, character, the efficiency of the criminal justice system, profit, drugs, and alcohol.

Although research on financial crime has expanded throughout time, little has been done to determine the relevance of the correlation between the factors that contribute to financial crime and its prevalence in various nations. This study would fill this gap by examining whether there is a statistically significant correlation between the level of financial crime and the identified determinant of financial crime.

The problem this study tends to address has existed long before (Bucur, 2011) and has been studied by different researchers. However, some scholars like Afonso & Rodrigues (2021) Avortri and Agbanyo (2020) have questioned whether high levels of crime and corruption can impede political stability, governance, and GDP growth. This study, however, will flip the coin and examine the potential impact that increased GDP per capita (\$) could have on combating financial crime.

Prior research (Afonso & Rodrigues, 2021; Avortri & Agbanyo, 2020) has adopted the stylised research focus on financial crime and what it can cause with a limited survey of what influences the presence or absence of a positive variable like GDP per capita (\$), effective governance and political stability on reducing or worsening financial crime activities. This could be argued as a more proactive strategy to tackle financial crime than focusing on what it does to the variables.

If the GDP grows, with more money and transaction count, it may arguably lead to increased opportunities for financial crime. On the other hand, one could argue that enhanced regulation and monitoring, brought on by a flourishing economy, would serve as a disincentive.

Research Question

This study tends to answer following question:

Is there a significant relationship between the level of GDP per capita (\$) and financial crime in nations?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were derived from the research questions to enable the researcher to achieve the research aims and guide this study.

Null (H₀): GDP per capita does not exert a statistically significant influence on financial crime.

Alternative (H₁): GDP per capita exerts a statistically significant influence on financial crime.

2.0 Literature Review

The Financial Conduct Authority (FCA) (2013) defined financial crime as any criminal activity involving money, financial services, or markets, including any offence involving (a) fraud or dishonesty; (b) misconduct in, or misuse of information relating to, a financial market; (c) handling the proceeds of crime; or (d) financing terrorism. FCA (2013) reaffirmed under this definition that "offence" relates to an act or omission that would have been illegal if it occurred in the UK.

Achim and Borlea (2021) contend that while Letia (2014) claimed that financial crime encompasses all non-violent crimes that result in monetary losses for a person or organisation, it should also consider illicit activities like gambling, prostitution, drug smuggling, and human trafficking. One could argue that this refutes Letia's (2014) claim that financial crime is a non-violent activity because, for example, drug smuggling and people trafficking frequently entail coercion, threats, and violence.

Anitei and Lazar (2016) provided a more nuanced explanation of the idea, referring to it as a "business crime" that involves illegal actions and behaviours by people, groups, associations, and societies in relation to banking, business dealings, and customs utilising deceptive methods, cheating, forgery, and a breach of trust. This generally aligns with Letia's (2014) thorough portrayal of financial crime as a betrayal of trust, exploiting the perceived stability and dependability of banking, commercial, and financial operations to violate the confidence of others.

Financial crime is a serious problem that can have far-reaching negative consequences for individuals, businesses, and the economy. One of the key issues with a financial crime is that it sometimes goes undetected or unprosecuted, making it difficult to combat. Additionally, financial crime can be difficult to investigate and prosecute, especially when it involves complex financial transactions or international networks. It can have a devastating impact on the victims. For example, individuals who are the victims of financial fraud or embezzlement may lose their life savings, which can have a major impact on their financial stability and quality of life. Similarly, businesses that are the victims of financial crime may suffer significant financial losses, which can impact their ability to operate and even lead to bankruptcy.

Exploring GDP per capita (\$) as a Determinant of Financial Crime

Various social, behavioural, economic, and political factors, including opportunity, greed, poverty, unemployment, political stability/instability, inflation, government effectiveness/ineffectiveness, GDP growth/decline, and low income, have been asserted by various studies (Akanni et al. 2019, Alan 2018, Hamid et al. 2013, Achim et al. 2021) as determinants or influencers of financial crime activities. These are, however, influenced by the motive and intended gain of the financial crime activity as evidenced by the fact that it can be carried out in various ways by the perpetrators, whether individuals or corporations, especially in an ever-changing world, argues Anitei & Lazar (2016).

Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

GDP growth typically influences financial crime. (Goel & Ram 2013, IMF 2020). When GDP depletes, people may be more likely to engage in illegal activities to make money and sustain life. Additionally, it can create other derivative problems like unemployment, which can create a sense of desperation and hopelessness and eventually drive people to commit financial crimes. GDP decline can also result in inflation and a high-interest rate which may affect the financial crime level, because when interest rates are high, borrowing and bad debt problems emerge for both individuals and businesses, leading to financial stress. This stress can potentially drive people to commit financial crimes to make ends meet. Conversely, increased GDP can influence financial crime as more money is available to steal. (IMF, 2020). It is difficult to draw definitive conclusions about the relationship between these variables and financial crime without a tested generalizable hypothesis.

The studies by De Rosa et al. (2010), IMF (2020), and Goel and Ram (2013), targeted at finding whether the growth or decline of GDP per capita lowered financial crime level or not have provided the background for the development of hypothesis three where the Null (H₀) assumed that GDP per capita does not exert a statistically significant influence on financial crime and the Alternative (H₁) hypothesis assuming that GDP per capita exerts a statistically significant influence on financial crime.

De Rosa et al. (2010), in an empirical study, demonstrated that a statistically significant relationship exists between economic development, which the researcher measured using GDP, and the level of financial crime. A similar study by IMF (2020) on Central America, which is one of the world's most violent regions, (IMF, 2020), revealed that a one percent increase in observed GDP per capita lowered crime by about 0.5 percent. The study further revealed that with the growth in GDP, productivity increased, lifting overall income, and producing more incentivized individuals who preferred to engage in legal businesses and paid jobs than to engage in criminal activity. This, the researcher argued has made financial crime become less attractive.

The results of these investigations were substantiated by the study by Goel and Ram (2013) which showed that GDP growth reduced financial crime levels. These studies can be argued to demonstrate that a growing GDP may enhance living conditions, lead to additional regulation, monitoring, and resources for law enforcement to investigate and punish financial crimes and raise public knowledge of financial crimes, which can deter them. Developed economies, usually characterized by increased GDP (De Rosa et al., 2010; Gundlach & Paldam, 2009) have been proven to experience lower financial crime levels when compared to developing economies, especially because GDP growth produces sound economic development, better law enforcement and compliance which is in contrast in developing economies or countries with lower GDP that have a high probability of criminal conduct and corruption.

Wahl et al. (2010), Yamen et al (2019) and Asghar et al. (2016). De Rosa (2010), IMF (2020), Goel & Ram (2013), and Gundlach & Paldam (2009) demonstrated in their empirical research that GDP growth has a significant correlation with the financial crime level as improved GDP growth produced a lesser financial crime level.

3.0 Methodology

This study used a quantitative research method, using secondary data from the World Bank Governance Indicators. The sample consisted of 155 countries, representing 71% of the total population. The year 2021 was chosen as it was the most recent year available on the World Bank indicator database, making it more representative of the current situation. The data was collected from the World Bank Governance Indicator, which provides the most up-to-date global development statistics. (World Bank, 2023) The World Bank calculates scores between -2.5 (weak) and 2.5 (strong). The data was analysed using R-studio, with descriptive statistics using mean, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation. Histograms were used to illustrate the statistical results. Results were tested using regression analysis, including the t-test and correlation coefficients, at a 0.05 level of significance to ensure solid evidence. The descriptive statistics summarize the data set used in the study, focusing on the mean, minimum, and maximum values of the variables under study.

Table 1 summarizes the variables used in the study, focusing more on the mean, minimum and maximum values of the variables under study.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Min	Max	Std Deviation
Financial Crime Level	0.01	-1.61	2.37	0.99
GDP per capita (\$)	18636.7	221.5	234315.5	29233.26

The GDP per capita has a mean value of \$18,636.7 which demonstrates the average for the entire sample. With the values of GDP per capita ranging from \$221.5 to \$234,315.5 as indicated by the minimum and maximum values, the level of economic development (measured by GDP per capita) is not the same across the sampled countries, indicating that the countries are at different levels of economic development. The standard deviation of \$29,233.26 also substantiates that the GDP per capita level of the sampled countries was significantly at variance since the standard deviation is greater than the mean.

Assessing the Distributional Properties of the Data Using Histogram

Graphing the data associated with the sampled countries displays the distributional properties of the data as presented in the figures below:

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

The distributional properties of GDP per capita are positively skewed, as evidenced in Figure 4.4 (Kalton & Conway, 2019), with much of the data closer to the centre (0). This indicates that most of the sampled countries have a very low level of GDP per capita which could be an indicator of low economic development. Again, the data for GDP per capita (\$) shows no normality in distribution.

Correlation Coefficient Analysis

The correlation between two variables is a proxy for the strength of their linear link. The table below displays the relationship between financial crime and GDP per capita (\$). The Pearson correlation coefficient was utilized to ascertain the nature and direction of the link between the variables.

The correlation coefficient's values fall between -1 and 1. The absolute value of the correlation coefficient denotes the strength, with higher values indicating stronger links and lower values indicating weaker interactions (David, 2009). The sign of the correlation coefficient reflects the direction of the association (positive or negative). Each variable has a perfect positive linear relationship with itself, resulting in correlation coefficients on the major diagonal of 1.0.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

Variables	Correlation Coefficient
Financial Crime Level and GDP per capita (\$)	0.0446

A positive correlation was observed between financial crime level and GDP per capita (\$). The correlation coefficient of 0.0446 indicates a very weak relationship between financial crime level and GDP per capita. This implies that the relationship between financial crime level and GDP per capita was minimal.

The correlation plots are depicted by the figures below:

Figure 3: Plot of financial crime level against GDP per capita (\$).

Figure 3 above demonstrates that the higher the correlation between the two variables, or the stronger the association, the more closely the data points resemble a straight line when plotted. The variables have a positive correlation if the data points form a straight line from close to the origin to high y-values, as shown by the correlation plots (David, 2009).

Multivariate Regression Analysis

A multivariate regression analysis explores the relationships between multiple independent variables and a single dependent variable (Frost, 2017). The controlling variables employed for the multi-regression model are government effectiveness, political stability, inflation, and voice & accountability.

Multicollinearity Check

To validate the independent and controlling variables, a multi-collinearity check was performed to ensure the validity and reliability of the regression analysis results.

Table 3: Multicollinearity Check Table

Variables	GDP per capita	Government Effectiveness	Political Stability	Inflation	Voice & Accountability.
GDP per capita (\$)				0.15	0.04
Government Effectiveness	-0.04		0.27	0.06	0.10
Political Stability	0.02			-0.01	-0.07
Inflation			-0.01		-0.13
Voice & Accountability					

Hint: independent variables cannot be checked against themselves, and the already checked ones may feature again in the table and are left blank since the result has been presented in previous boxes.

Multicollinearity is often indicated by an absolute correlation coefficient of >0.7 between two or more predictors (Gilbert, 2009). Since the correlation coefficients reported in Table 3 did not exceed 0.7 in any of the cases, the regression model is free from multicollinearity problems. As such, its results would be reliable.

The Multivariate Model

This study built two multivariate models, namely, the linear regression model and the log-linear regression model:

Financial crime level= $f(\text{GDP per capita } (\$), \text{ government effectiveness, political stability, inflation, voice \& accountability})$.

Econometrically:

Model 1:

Financial crime level= $\beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{GDP per capita } (\$) + \beta_2 \cdot \text{government effectiveness} + \beta_3 \cdot \text{political stability} + \beta_4 \cdot \text{inflation} + \beta_5 \cdot \text{voice \& accountability}$.

Model 2:

(log) Financial crime level= $\beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{GDP per capita } (\$) + \beta_2 \cdot \text{government effectiveness} + \beta_3 \cdot \text{political stability} + \beta_4 \cdot \text{inflation} + \beta_5 \cdot \text{voice \& accountability}$.

These two models were built to determine the best-fitting equation that describes the linear relationship between GDP per capita (\$) and financial crime level (Frost, 2017). The regression outcome demonstrates how each independent variable affected the dependent variable (Roback & Legler, 2016). The regression coefficient values, which vary from 0% to 100%, show how much of an impact there is (Frost, 2017). The F statistics, R-squared, and Adjusted R-squared of the models were compared, and the best model was selected based on the results.

Table 4: Linear Regression Model (Model 1) and Log-Linear Regression Model (Model 2)

Independent variable	Model 1 (Linear)	Model 2 (Log-linear)
GDP per capita (\$)	0.000*	0.0000
Government effectiveness	0.0920***	1.0480***
Political stability	-0.0007	0.0100
R-squared	0.8312	0.473
Adjusted R-squared	0.8256	0.4319
F-statistics	148.7	11.49
P-value (F-statistics)	0.000***	0.000***

Hint - Significance level: 0 ‘***’ 0.001 ‘**’ 0.01 ‘*’ 0.05 ‘.’ 0.1 ‘ ’ 1

- For this study, the researcher adopted a 5% level of significance.

Table 4 above presents the linear and log-linear regression coefficient estimates, respectively. The optimal or best model is selected based on the Adjusted R-squared and F-statistic values that evaluate how accurately a statistical model can forecast a result (Frost, 2017). Hence, the linear regression model (Model 1), which presented the highest Adjusted R-squared of 0.8256 and an F-statistic of 148.7 (compared to the log-linear model), was selected for the hypotheses testing.

Robustness Check

The evidence of heteroscedasticity or homoscedasticity during the robustness check will determine the acceptability and reliability of the multivariate model results (Roback & Legler, 2016). Heteroscedasticity tests are used to detect the presence of heteroscedasticity in a regression model and to assess the validity of the assumption of constant variance of errors. Homoscedasticity implies that the variability of errors is consistent and does not systematically change with the values of the independent variable(s). Homoscedasticity is an important assumption in linear regression, as violations of this assumption can affect the accuracy and reliability of the statistical inferences drawn from the model (Achim & Borlea, 2020).

The Breusch-Pagan Test

The Breusch-Pagan test, a widely used test for heteroscedasticity (Frost, 2017), was adopted for this study.

The below hypotheses were used to check for robustness and to determine if the model is statistically adequate.

H0: There is homoscedasticity

H1: There is heteroscedasticity

Table 5: The Breusch-Pagan test

	BP	df	p-value
Model 1	5.7107	5	0.3354

Table 5 above presents the result of the Breusch-Pagan heteroscedasticity test, evidencing that the model is free from significant heteroscedasticity as shown by the *Breusch-Pagan test p-value of 0.3354, greater than 0.05, informing the acceptance of the residuals as*

homoscedastic. In line with this, the null hypothesis (H₀) is accepted, validating ‘there is homoscedasticity’.

4.0 Discussion of findings

Examining the impact of GDP growth on all World Bank member countries’ financial crime levels in the year 2021; GDP per capita has a positive and statistically significant estimated coefficient. This shows that an increase in economic development brings about high financial crime.

Hypotheses Testing: For this study, the coefficients and the p-value of the multi-regression model were considered. For instance, if the probability value is less than 0.05, the variable is adjudged significant, and vice versa if the p-value is greater than 0.05.

Hypotheses:

Null (H₀): GDP per capita does not exert a statistically significant influence on financial crime.

Alternative (H₁): GDP per capita exerts a statistically significant influence on financial crime.

The linear regression result indicates that the GDP per capita of the sampled economies does not significantly cause a decline in the level of financial crime. This finding is based on the positive coefficient of the GDP per capita featured on the regression model result. The p-value ($0.0226 < 0.05$) informed the decision to reject the null hypothesis in favour of the alternative hypothesis. This implies that the financial crime level of the sampled countries significantly increases at the slightest increase in the GDP per capita level. This negates the generally held belief that when GDP rises, and employment opportunities are created, people are discouraged from engaging in illegal activities to make money and sustain their lives (De Rosa et al., 2010; IMF, 2020; Goel & Ram, 2013).

The reason for this result could arguably be that the perpetrators of financial crime may be driven by factors other than economic factors. For instance, Akanni et al. (2019) found that social and behavioural factors other than economic factors have been found to be responsible for the high level of financial crime. However, the finding of this study contradicts those of IMF (2020); Goel and Ram (2013), who had earlier reported that an increase in GDP lowered the level of financial crime. This disparity in the findings could be linked to the fact that the geography of the countries studied differs in terms of economic dynamics, size, and level of development. For instance, (De Rosa et al., 2010; Gundlach & Paldam, 2009) affirmed that well-developed economies with large GDP experiences lower financial crime levels when compared to developing economies because GDP growth produces sound economic development, better law enforcement, and compliance which is in not so in developing economies where the GDP level is not sustainable, leading to a high propensity of financial criminality.

5.0 Conclusions

This study explored the link between GDP per capita (\$) and financial crime, to bring new solutions/approaches to the problem, due to the complexity of the manifestation forms of financial crime phenomena.

This study sought to unravel whether GDP per capita lowers financial crime levels, established that GDP per capita was positive and statistically significant. The implication of this is that increase in the GDP per capita in 2021 did not help to reduce financial crime, but rather financial crime increased substantially.

6.0 Recommendation

The study's finding that GDP per capita positively and significantly correlates with financial crime challenges the traditional assumption that economic growth inherently reduces criminal activity. Instead, it highlights that rising income levels, without corresponding improvements in governance, regulation, and enforcement, may create more opportunities for financial misconduct. Therefore, policymakers should adopt a multi-dimensional approach that goes beyond economic metrics, strengthening institutional frameworks, improving law enforcement, promoting ethical standards, and incorporating governance indicators into risk assessments. As GDP growth alone does not deter financial crime, particularly in countries with weak regulatory systems, comprehensive and context-specific strategies that integrate social, legal, and institutional reforms are essential to effectively combat financial crime in both developing and advanced economies.

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APPENDIX

Data collected and refined for analysis.

No	Year	Country Name	Country Code	Control of Corruption (Financial Crime Level)	Government Effectiveness	Political Stability	GDP per capita (\$)	Inflation	Voice & Accountability
1	2021	Albania	ALB	-0.555924177	-0.00336	0.109446	6492.872	2.04147	0.09120497
2	2021	Algeria	DZA	-0.614184439	-0.62076	-0.87647	3690.628	7.22606	-1.0095193
3	2021	Angola	AGO	-0.655345798	-1.05937	-0.71084	1953.534	25.7543	-0.840916
4	2021	Antigua and Barbuda	ATG	0.26372695	-0.14225	0.955552	15781.4	2.063	0.73925132
5	2021	Armenia	ARM	0.072149873	-0.24956	-0.83559	4966.513	7.18484	0.05920416
6	2021	Australia	AUS	1.73749423	1.51293	0.850989	60443.11	2.86391	1.3794421
7	2021	Austria	AUT	1.271236777	1.57001	0.914891	53637.71	2.76667	1.3985666
8	2021	Azerbaijan	AZE	-0.827584863	0.24768	-0.85348	5387.998	6.6503	-1.5304976
9	2021	Bahamas, The	BHS	1.181445718	0.4618	0.876719	27478.39	2.90491	0.91377217
10	2021	Bahrain	BHR	0.168159813	0.71713	-0.50511	26562.97	-0.60632	-1.5015956
11	2021	Bangladesh	BGD	-0.962003231	-0.62741	-0.97016	2457.925	5.54565	-0.7696443
12	2021	Belarus	BLR	-0.23533681	-0.77082	-0.73661	7302.258	9.46028	-1.5838302
13	2021	Belgium	BEL	1.484489679	1.12509	0.612555	51247.01	2.44025	1.28270888
14	2021	Belize	BLZ	-0.304920167	-0.48897	0.460717	6228.267	3.23564	0.55050194
15	2021	Benin	BEN	-0.154652014	-0.20667	-0.30134	1319.155	1.73354	-0.2375402
16	2021	Bhutan	BTN	1.553735256	0.79633	0.973133	3266.365	7.34684	0.22564517
17	2021	Bolivia	BOL	-0.86410296	-0.73192	-0.31857	3345.197	0.73738	-0.1099207
18	2021	Bosnia and Herzegovina	BIH	-0.643698514	-1.04125	-0.38058	7143.311	1.98164	-0.3133234
19	2021	Botswana	BWA	0.685204029	0.35407	0.978378	6805.221	7.24098	0.45758614
20	2021	Brazil	BRA	-0.477816075	-0.46029	-0.48501	7507.161	8.30166	0.2781969
21	2021	Brunei Darussalam	BRN	1.246438384	1.45483	1.168644	31449.08	1.73341	-0.8482108
22	2021	Bulgaria	BGR	-0.235711768	-0.13918	0.458269	12221.5	3.29774	0.29090291
23	2021	Burkina Faso	BFA	-0.059376009	-0.72633	-1.63874	893.0772	3.65353	-0.1093084
24	2021	Burundi	BDI	-1.580753326	-1.33109	-1.36398	221.4777	8.40454	-1.4051549
25	2021	Cabo Verde	CPV	1.035422206	0.04274	0.902458	3293.233	1.86215	0.9390173
26	2021	Cambodia	KHM	-1.176956654	-0.42264	-0.13212	1625.235	2.92073	-1.4358532
27	2021	Cameroon	CMR	-1.09271419	-0.87531	-1.40651	1666.933	2.27186	-1.1601563
28	2021	Canada	CAN	1.64609468	1.60389	0.936903	51987.94	3.39519	1.45788443
29	2021	Central African Republic	CAF	-1.226334929	-1.64427	-2.10454	461.1375	4.25936	-1.195578
30	2021	Chad	TCD	-1.477722049	-1.42402	-1.33554	685.6903	-0.77284	-1.4201199
31	2021	Chile	CHL	0.98372668	0.62607	0.062637	16265.1	4.52457	0.96785426
32	2021	China	CHN	0.053693742	0.84067	-0.48186	12556.33	0.98102	-1.6365763
33	2021	Colombia	COL	-0.344050169	-0.01456	-0.91408	6104.137	3.49506	0.09971508
34	2021	Congo, Rep.	COG	-1.37306428	-1.5511	-0.60662	2290.383	1.71564	-1.2380776
35	2021	Costa Rica	CRI	0.495704889	0.25731	0.872773	12472.44	1.72648	1.09140074
36	2021	Cote d'Ivoire	CIV	-0.371892631	-0.50191	-0.95286	2549.041	4.09195	-0.4710795
37	2021	Croatia	HRV	0.061275687	0.59104	0.707874	17685.33	2.55451	0.60984164
38	2021	Cyprus	CYP	0.394521177	0.73613	0.443114	31551.82	2.44609	0.86566663

39	2021	Czech Republic	CZE	0.641104996	1.11025	0.957601	26821.25	3.83984	1.01879382
40	2021	Denmark	DNK	2.366175175	2.00407	0.949907	68007.76	1.85305	1.55789542
41	2021	Dominican Republic	DOM	-0.569274545	0.031	0.137411	8476.752	8.243	0.30179748
42	2021	Ecuador	ECU	-0.573393404	-0.20915	-0.26625	5965.133	0.13325	0.10613444
43	2021	Egypt, Arab Rep.	EGY	-0.684838116	-0.43211	-1.02421	3698.835	5.21405	-1.5097785
44	2021	El Salvador	SLV	-0.532646835	-0.31268	-0.21123	4551.185	3.46693	-0.0552323
45	2021	Estonia	EST	1.535825491	1.38256	0.755604	27943.7	4.65317	1.19077373
46	2021	Ethiopia	ETH	-0.397181958	-0.61324	-2.06836	925.0774	26.8395	-1.0691051
47	2021	Fiji	FJI	0.47165674	0.62381	0.667942	4646.613	0.15586	-0.1503408
48	2021	Finland	FIN	2.270076752	1.96044	0.981908	53654.75	2.19457	1.62274849
49	2021	France	FRA	1.310407043	1.26752	0.371734	43658.98	1.64233	1.11508608
50	2021	Gambia, The	GMB	-0.358450145	-0.63848	0.175201	772.1524	7.37035	-0.1028912
51	2021	Georgia	GEO	0.688035369	0.65421	-0.42343	5023.274	9.56691	0.01531827
52	2021	Germany	DEU	1.813231826	1.33115	0.755996	51203.55	3.14297	1.43199122
53	2021	Ghana	GHA	-0.106090412	-0.14948	0.066448	2363.299	9.97109	0.46734911
54	2021	Greece	GRC	0.207244009	0.44355	0.154484	20192.6	1.22383	0.95542896
55	2021	Grenada	GRD	0.523264706	0.02653	1.04173	9010.572	1.21951	0.73408788
56	2021	Guatemala	GTM	-1.173671126	-0.75177	-0.39217	5025.542	4.26105	-0.4618636
57	2021	Guinea	GIN	-0.996127367	-0.91567	-0.97041	1189.176	12.5971	-0.9875714
58	2021	Guinea-Bissau	GNB	-1.300152063	-1.42388	-0.28024	795.1186	2.24249	-0.2363185
59	2021	Guyana	GUY	-0.165203333	-0.23673	-0.1438	9998.544	5.03286	0.24670784
60	2021	Haiti	HTI	-1.423377037	-2.18749	-1.09535	1829.593	16.8415	-0.9521484
61	2021	Honduras	HND	-1.072395802	-0.78213	-0.612	2771.717	4.48088	-0.5871212
62	2021	Hong Kong SAR, China	HKG	1.709560752	1.52612	0.261169	49800.54	1.56876	-0.211014
63	2021	Hungary	HUN	0.035607804	0.63451	0.861372	18728.12	5.11097	0.40406024
64	2021	Iceland	ISL	1.790595531	1.63863	1.373475	68727.64	4.44424	1.37459934
65	2021	India	IND	-0.294859201	0.28236	-0.61504	2256.59	5.13141	0.11272161
66	2021	Indonesia	IDN	-0.427905589	0.37901	-0.50647	4332.709	1.56013	0.15521753
67	2021	Iran, Islamic Rep.	IRN	-1.096301556	-0.85807	-1.62163	4091.209	43.389	-1.4702708
68	2021	Iraq	IRQ	-1.250528455	-1.29181	-2.39699	4775.377	6.04186	-0.9629664
69	2021	Ireland	IRL	1.649120331	1.50441	0.856822	100172.1	2.35814	1.43021321
70	2021	Israel	ISR	0.855771303	1.29197	-1.06135	52170.71	1.49229	0.68261665
71	2021	Italy	ITA	0.542555928	0.3612	0.578434	35657.5	1.87378	1.09520352
72	2021	Jamaica	JAM	-0.029271552	0.41401	0.223474	5183.581	5.86278	0.62797612
73	2021	Japan	JPN	1.565421462	1.40276	1.027348	39312.66	-0.23335	1.07693446
74	2021	Jordan	JOR	0.05046254	0.2274	-0.27573	4103.259	1.34609	-0.7991566
75	2021	Kenya	KEN	-0.713267028	-0.32999	-1.08966	2081.8	6.11091	-0.3662771
76	2021	Korea, Rep.	KOR	0.759860098	1.40621	0.662571	34997.78	2.49833	0.9311831
77	2021	Kosovo	XKX	-0.318530053	-0.22341	-0.12038	5269.784	3.35369	-0.079332
78	2021	Kyrgyz Republic	KGZ	-1.124733806	-0.72709	-0.42594	1276.7	11.905	-0.6054688
79	2021	Lao PDR	LAO	-1.03965342	-0.61772	0.726246	2535.623	3.75562	-1.6816999
80	2021	Latvia	LVA	0.746790171	0.87274	0.687567	21148.16	3.27583	0.90630883

81	2021	Lebanon	LBN	-1.22970438	-1.28704	-1.49348	4136.146	154.756	-0.6256257
82	2021	Lesotho	LSO	-0.315276623	-0.91377	-0.21959	1094.098	6.04775	-0.0198031
83	2021	Lithuania	LTU	0.851239979	1.05661	0.81543	23723.34	4.68354	1.04088652
84	2021	Luxembourg	LUX	1.871590853	1.71904	1.20638	133590.1	2.52692	1.5082804
85	2021	Madagascar	MDG	-0.933383822	-1.00036	-0.63593	500.511	5.81225	-0.2700881
86	2021	Malaysia	MYS	0.170527324	0.99169	0.138853	11109.26	2.4771	-0.1547223
87	2021	Maldives	MDV	-0.371216476	0.3864	0.502794	10366.29	0.54315	-0.2384848
88	2021	Mali	MLI	-0.867007017	-1.22319	-2.35244	873.7949	3.9256	-0.7774898
89	2021	Malta	MLT	0.31758076	0.89264	0.972676	33486.67	1.49789	1.08168638
90	2021	Mauritania	MRT	-0.821054399	-0.73372	-0.67025	2166.047	3.56516	-0.7652194
91	2021	Mauritius	MUS	0.467553556	0.8494	0.85581	9106.237	4.02853	0.66472882
92	2021	Mexico	MEX	-1.001628876	-0.31216	-0.63674	10045.68	5.68921	-0.0741874
93	2021	Moldova	MDA	-0.447890878	-0.40499	-0.20552	5230.662	5.10641	0.04762687
94	2021	Mongolia	MNG	-0.528645813	-0.46718	0.654302	4566.14	7.35281	0.3188701
95	2021	Montenegro	MNE	-0.019546321	0.00613	-0.14892	9465.704	2.4108	0.17449017
96	2021	Morocco	MAR	-0.433994025	-0.06678	-0.39608	3795.38	1.40196	-0.607271
97	2021	Mozambique	MOZ	-0.811555684	-0.76534	-1.22819	491.8391	5.68849	-0.6125438
98	2021	Namibia	NAM	0.258660823	0.05935	0.547819	4865.558	3.61691	0.57228744
99	2021	Nepal	NPL	-0.530735135	-0.87153	-0.24301	1208.219	4.08791	-0.0891101
100	2021	Netherlands	NLD	2.035641909	1.76668	0.915173	57767.88	2.67572	1.50255418
101	2021	New Zealand	NZL	2.201695204	1.35075	1.438624	48781.03	3.94112	1.62185359
102	2021	Nicaragua	NIC	-1.236290574	-0.8523	-0.46714	2045.535	4.92841	-1.2870005
103	2021	Niger	NER	-0.546674609	-0.61456	-1.6163	590.6295	3.83787	-0.3871441
104	2021	Nigeria	NGA	-1.070116878	-0.996	-1.7793	2065.749	16.9528	-0.6365556
105	2021	North Macedonia	MKD	-0.351957202	-0.08426	0.124912	6694.641	3.23075	0.14148904
106	2021	Norway	NOR	2.14091754	1.83936	1.103745	89154.28	3.48388	1.75175452
107	2021	Oman	OMN	0.086335801	-0.11808	0.506666	19509.47	1.54664	-1.1929884
108	2021	Pakistan	PAK	-0.785676658	-0.40269	-1.66678	1505.01	9.49621	-0.8405113
109	2021	Palau	PLW	-0.428823858	-0.2777	0.950392	12083.89	2.61248	1.05862057
110	2021	Panama	PAN	-0.570509851	0.1594	0.285786	14617.6	1.6307	0.54977256
111	2021	Papua New Guinea	PNG	-0.755582631	-0.88746	-0.58185	2672.946	4.48359	0.02295998
112	2021	Paraguay	PRY	-1.007155418	-0.62293	-0.00299	5891.5	4.78798	0.00905482
113	2021	Peru	PER	-0.63322556	-0.26079	-0.40597	6621.574	4.27166	0.18160866
114	2021	Philippines	PHL	-0.508519769	0.07033	-0.92892	3460.531	3.92718	-0.1504983
115	2021	Poland	POL	0.572010398	0.29278	0.51243	17999.91	5.05503	0.58724451
116	2021	Portugal	PRT	0.768555641	0.99131	0.952886	24567.51	1.26566	1.2580446
117	2021	Qatar	QAT	0.806125164	1.11364	0.95788	66838.36	2.30447	-1.1749094
118	2021	Romania	ROU	-0.037915125	-0.12964	0.533032	14858.23	5.05233	0.6020245
119	2021	Russian Federation	RUS	-0.900473714	-0.1761	-0.64544	12194.78	6.69446	-1.1018852
120	2021	Rwanda	RWA	0.599220455	0.26119	0.170439	822.348	-0.39135	-0.9554023
121	2021	Samoa	WSM	0.625925839	0.44313	1.109918	3857.318	3.1332	0.72614974
122	2021	Saudi Arabia	SAU	0.306925714	0.49631	-0.58386	23185.87	3.06329	-1.5906439
123	2021	Serbia	SRB	-0.437255442	0.04743	-0.13423	9230.178	4.0851	-0.1236479
124	2021	Sierra Leone	SLE	-0.431214958	-1.11451	-0.16455	480.0392	11.874	-0.0636349

125	2021	Singapore	SGP	2.171539545	2.29149	1.49319	72794	2.30486	-0.136062
126	2021	Slovak Republic	SVK	0.235205427	0.52921	0.559577	21391.93	3.14961	0.91435641
127	2021	Slovenia	SVN	0.71923095	1.1782	0.760044	29291.4	1.91707	0.91466957
128	2021	Solomon Islands	SLB	-0.140978411	-0.91164	0.490975	2304.845	-0.11544	0.46907106
129	2021	South Africa	ZAF	0.022103222	-0.01744	-0.70658	7055.045	4.61167	0.78849739
130	2021	Spain	ESP	0.741642237	0.94727	0.579051	30103.51	3.09314	1.010028
131	2021	Sri Lanka	LKA	-0.334563583	-0.08303	-0.31793	4013.688	7.01478	-0.0696102
132	2021	St. Kitts and Nevis	KNA	0.438981831	0.41732	0.955552	18082.61	1.19569	0.78219742
133	2021	St. Lucia	LCA	0.586345255	-0.09064	0.853993	9414.226	2.4107	0.86482322
134	2021	St. Vincent and the Grenadines	VCT	0.803943515	0.30754	1.04173	8666.387	1.57273	0.87782824
135	2021	Sudan	SDN	-1.289687276	-1.6375	-1.93504	751.8214	382.816	-1.4681702
136	2021	Suriname	SUR	-0.396517456	-0.64507	0.374922	4869.134	59.1117	0.37689281
137	2021	Sweden	SWE	2.130344868	1.65234	1.034035	61028.74	2.1632	1.50559938
138	2021	Switzerland	CHE	1.989697456	2.03225	1.131445	91991.6	0.58181	1.55418313
139	2021	Tanzania	TZA	-0.355093211	-0.63178	-0.43697	1099.288	3.69092	-0.7116134
140	2021	Thailand	THA	-0.45705694	0.25308	-0.54578	7066.191	1.2304	-0.7905759
141	2021	Tonga	TON	-0.384434402	0.28339	1.074102	4426.001	5.64051	0.72931576
142	2021	Trinidad and Tobago	TTO	-0.277760476	0.19269	0.154863	16032.5	2.05923	0.67239875
143	2021	Tunisia	TUN	-0.229555964	-0.16706	-0.69575	3807.139	5.70635	0.18709853
144	2021	Turkiye	TUR	-0.385957003	-0.0866	-1.09809	9661.236	19.5965	-0.8591428
145	2021	Uganda	UGA	-0.998556554	-0.57023	-0.85966	883.892	2.20457	-0.8217646
146	2021	Ukraine	UKR	-0.766656518	-0.40897	-1.09882	4835.572	9.36314	0.07631124
147	2021	United Kingdom	GBR	1.670565367	1.27948	0.542117	46510.28	2.51837	1.29843295
148	2021	United States	USA	1.046862006	1.33641	0.004954	70248.63	4.69786	0.90390658
149	2021	Uruguay	URY	1.61529088	0.83995	1.046311	17313.19	7.74791	1.29830694
150	2021	Uzbekistan	UZB	-0.808077157	-0.1968	-0.2398	1983.065	10.8492	-1.3997523
151	2021	Vanuatu	VUT	-0.017598171	-0.55845	0.791273	2996.621	2.34328	0.6939553
152	2021	Vietnam	VNM	-0.285784245	0.27798	-0.1146	3756.489	1.83472	-1.3042051
153	2021	West Bank and Gaza	PSE	-0.738599837	-0.76679	-1.83927	3663.969	1.23748	-1.110767
154	2021	Zambia	ZMB	-0.753424048	-0.81693	0.060216	1137.344	22.0212	-0.3669986
155	2021	Zimbabwe	ZWE	-1.257896781	-1.24293	-1.02678	1773.92	98.5461	-1.1369342